

Heavy Equipment Company

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12771333>

jam kerja receiving truk

Jam kerja receive truk	
shift	Hr
1	8
2	6.5
3	7
total	21.5

Heavy Equipment Company

Gambar flow process/activity

Proses di Heavy Equipment Company
(sumber : data Perusahaan)

No	Tanggal	in	Durasi total	Nama Drive	Nopol	Subcont	Waktu Antar Kedatangan	Driver Report to Security (dalam menit)	Operator Check Unload Priority (Dalam menit)	Check Material (dalam menit)	Unload Material to Storage
1	19 juni 2022	9:15	1:27	Driver 1	Bxxxxxx	PT 1	0:00	0:05	0:07	0:05	1:10
2	19 juni 2022	10:00	1:38	Driver 2	Bxxxxxx	PT 2	0:45	0:05	0:08	0:05	1:20
3	19 juni 2022	11:00	1:42	Driver 3	Bxxxxxx	PT 3	1:00	0:03	0:09	0:05	1:25
4	19 juni 2022	12:00	1:48	Driver 4	Bxxxxxx	PT 4	1:00	0:02	0:11	0:05	1:30
5	19 juni 2022	13:00	1:31	Driver 5	Bxxxxxx	PT 5	1:00	0:03	0:09	0:04	1:15
6	19 juni 2022	13:30	1:30	Driver 6	Bxxxxxx	PT 6	0:30	0:03	0:12	0:04	1:11
7	19 juni 2022	14:20	1:23	Driver 7	Bxxxxxx	PT 7	0:50	0:03	0:10	0:05	1:05
8	19 juni 2022	14:50	1:26	Driver 8	Bxxxxxx	PT 8	0:30	0:04	0:08	0:04	1:10
9	19 juni 2022	15:55	1:30	Driver 9	Bxxxxxx	PT 9	1:05	0:05	0:07	0:05	1:13
10	19 juni 2022	16:30	1:34	Driver 10	Bxxxxxx	PT 10	0:35	0:05	0:08	0:05	1:16
11	19 juni 2022	16:55	1:41	Driver 11	Bxxxxxx	PT 11	0:25	0:05	0:09	0:05	1:22
12	19 juni 2022	19:00	1:31	Driver 12	Bxxxxxx	PT 12	2:05	0:05	0:11	0:05	1:10
13	19 juni 2022	19:30	1:26	Driver 13	Bxxxxxx	PT 13	0:30	0:05	0:12	0:04	1:05
14	19 juni 2022	20:20	1:30	Driver 14	Bxxxxxx	PT 7	0:50	0:05	0:10	0:05	1:10
15	19 juni 2022	20:30	1:23	Driver 15	Bxxxxxx	PT 7	0:10	0:03	0:12	0:05	1:03
16	19 juni 2022	21:45	1:21	Driver 16	Bxxxxxx	PT 6	1:15	0:03	0:07	0:05	1:06
17	19 juni 2022	23:00	1:16	Driver 17	Bxxxxxx	PT 7	1:15	0:03	0:08	0:05	1:00
18	19 juni 2022	23:00	1:16	Driver 18	Bxxxxxx	PT 7	0:00	0:03	0:07	0:04	1:02

data Input Analyzer

Proses	distribusi	expression
Waktu Antar Kedatangan	<i>Normal</i>	NORM(42.5, 29.5)
<i>Driver Report to Security</i>	<i>beta</i>	1.5 + 4 * BETA(1.38, 0.93)
<i>Operator check unload priority</i>	<i>beta</i>	6.5 + 6 * BETA(0.744, 0.93)
<i>Check Material</i>	<i>triangular</i>	TRIA(3.5, 5.17, 5.5)
<i>Unload Material to Storage</i>	<i>weibull</i>	59.5 + WEIB(13.6, 1.49)

Hasil output simulasi

output simulasi		
No	dalam jam	konversi dalam menit
1	1.7419865	104.5
2	1.4057765	84.3
3	1.4210062	85.3
4	1.5223381	91.3
5	1.2940174	77.6
6	1.5447935	92.7
7	1.4003196	84.0
8	1.5603089	93.6
9	1.2326106	74.0
10	1.6096786	96.6
11	1.3934338	83.6
12	1.5495152	93.0
13	1.6014562	96.1
14	1.5488683	92.9
15	1.6662154	100.0
16	1.3834321	83.0
17	1.8772076	112.6
18	1.2973473	77.8
rata rata	1.5027951	90.2
Standar deviasi	0.1656765	9.9
variansi	0.027448703	98.81532976
n	18	
n-1	17	
confidence interval	5%	0.05
maka Z $\alpha/2$	1.96	